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Organic Agriculture Contribution to the Rural Tourism Development in the North of Montenegro

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Abstract

This research was conducted in order to determine the benefits that local communities in Montenegro can achieve by developing rural tourism. The main aim of this paper is to establish how organic agriculture can contribute to the rural tourism development. This research is non-experimental, based on the content analysis, observation method, case study method, and questionnaire. The obtained results showed that organic agriculture contributes to the development of rural tourism by creating a special niche market, giving the additional value to the product, providing tourists with the possibility of education on organic agriculture as well as contributing to the destination differentiation. Participation in the preparation of healthy food as well as in the rural jobs is the most interesting activity for tourists. Rural tourism also contributes to the creation or expansion of the organic product market. In order for organic agriculture to contribute to the rural tourism development in Montenegro, it is necessary to develop the awareness of youth about the significance and benefits that it provides by allowing the children to visit organic farms and participate in organic agriculture activities. There should be organized events which include public presentations on organic agriculture processes and the possibility of discussion with organic farmers. Another thing to be done is to expand the organic food market. It is also necessary to enable the promotion of every interested rural household through the internet and advertise domestic products through national television in order to protect them and support organic producers.

Key Words: Local community development, Montenegrin rural areas, Organic agriculture, Rural tourism.

1. Introduction

Montenegro, known as the last unspoiled place in Europe, is one of the most famous tourist destinations around the world. The importance of tourism for Montenegro is of priceless value. The data shows that this branch of economy represents over 25% of GDP (Tourism development strategy of Montenegro until 2020).

Considering the natural potential that makes Montenegro a competitive destination, it is understandable that in recent years tourists are more and more interested in Montenegrin rural areas. However, in addition to all the preconditions Montenegro has for rural tourism development, there are a number of aggravating circumstances that decelerate this process. According to preliminary research, (A. Babović, A. Babović, & A. Babović 2015); (Despotović, Joksimović, Jovanović, & Svržnjak, 2017) among the main problems of the rural tourism development is inadequate accommodation capacity. The quality of accommodation does not satisfy the preferences of tourists, mostly prevail rooms that can not accommodate a group of tourists, and often remain empty. The locals consider that the state's investments in this type of tourism are not sufficient. Therefore the

majority of households cannot meet the basic requirements of tourists, e.g., suitable accommodation. Roads leading to households are mostly not paved. Households still do not make significant revenue in order to invest by themselves. Promotion of rural tourism is very poorly developed. Montenegro is mostly promoted as a "sun and sea" destination. Tourist organizations do not promote a specific destination, i.e., households in an appropriate manner so that even domestic tourists are not familiar with their offers. Inadequate workforce represents another significant problem. Household owners are mostly pensioners aged 60, and over, just few of them are farmers.

The agricultural sector can be integrated together with tourism in order to strengthen both sectors, and this is done through rural tourism (Borg 2013). In order to offer the new product and provide the new experience, the use of organic agriculture can help the future improvement of rural tourism. This will result in a new niche market for Montenegro. Consequently, the main goal of this research is to explain in which ways organic agriculture can contribute and support the policy of rural tourism development.

These are the main problems this research is focused on:

- Primarily, youth are not sufficiently educated in the field of organic agriculture. Their awareness of the organic agriculture importance and the benefits it provides is very low, which leads to a high migration degree and the lack of young workforce in the rural areas of Montenegro.
- Real estate fragmentation and nonexistence of the organic products market greatly impede the development of organic agriculture in Montenegro. This causes farmers to produce only for the needs of their households.
- Insufficient Government support for organic food producers - relates primarily to low subsidies and inadequate promotion and protection of Montenegrin organic products. This often causes distrust in the quality of organic products among consumers, they consider the price to be high, and they prefer to buy very cheap imported products.

2. Literature review

There are a large number of researches on a similar topic which mainly describe the different offers of many countries in rural tourism. As far as Montenegro is concerned, conducted researches usually concentrate on problems of underdevelopment of agro-tourism as well as socio-economic characteristics of the rural population.

2.1 *The main characteristic of rural areas in the north of Montenegro*

Rural areas cover more than 90% of the whole territory of Montenegro. The northern region encompasses 13 municipalities, and this is the biggest region according to number of rural villages. In the last 30 year, the number of inhabitants in northern region is constantly reducing (Despotović, Joksimović, & Jovanović, 2016). At the same time, agricultural production faces the same trend (Vujošević 2007). According to data provided by NGO "Euromost" from Bijelo Polje, the north of Montenegro which makes up more than half of the territory has lost 50,000 inhabitants in the last 25 years (www.pvinformer.me). As far as internal migrations are concerned, according to Monstat official data (2017), the negative migration balance was recorded only in the northern region of Montenegro, amounting to 1.268 persons. Residents mainly run away to the central and southern part of the country (www.monitor.co.me). Currently, one-third of the population is located in Podgorica, the capital. Research on Economic Migration from Montenegro to the European Union (2016), showed that a large number of residents mainly from the northern part seek asylum in Germany. In 2015 year, the 3.635 inhabitants of Montenegro filed a claim asylum in Germany (Radulović & Brnović, 2016). Previous analyzes have shown that the northern region has a share of only 18% in GDP (Milanović, Radojević, & Škatarić, 2010). From the unemployment view of point, it is particularly pronounced in the Northern Region (Radević & Theotokatos, 2011). Based on the statistical data of Employment Office on December 31, (2016) there were 49.487 unemployed persons (women 25.842 or 52.21%). The unemployment rate is particularly pronounced in Bijelo Polje 29.95%, Rozaje 28.93%, Kolasin 28.13%, while in Pljevlja it is 26.18% (Employment Office 2016). Agricultural activity has the smallest share in total employment, only 8.3% (Radović & Djurašković, 2016).

2.2 Structure of agricultural holdings in Montenegro

According to the last agricultural census (2010), the total number of farms in Montenegro was 48.870, of which 48.824 are family farms or 99%. The main characteristic of family farms is high proportion of older working-age population on the farm and a lack of young people. On family farms in Montenegro 6.717 persons were under 24 years old, which makes 6.83 %, while 23.198 working-age population is aged 65 and over, which makes 23.58% of the total workforce (Despotović et al., 2016). According to the Census of Agriculture (2010), women comprise only 12.87% of holders of family farms, while about 33.24% of holders of holdings are aged over 65 or more, and they are mostly man. When it comes to education of the labor force on family farms in Montenegro the highest share belongs to people with 4 years of high school, 33.74%, of which 66.88% are men and 33.22% are women. Only 1.47% has secondary or higher agricultural education, of which more than 70% are men. One of the most important demographic characteristic of rural villages in the northern region is their fragmentation. If we look at the number of members on the farm, most of those farms have 1 to 2 members, and they accounted to 76.8% (Vujošević 2007).

2.3 Brief explanation on rural tourism

As a result of industrialization and globalization, especially in developing countries, rural tourism has experienced an expansion. Rural tourism primarily relates to the agricultural environment, agricultural products and the stay of tourists in the rural area (Ljubišić 2017). The European Commission (1986) presented rural tourism as a broad concept that includes not only farm tourism or agrotourism—accommodation provided by farmers—but all tourist activities in rural areas. In rural areas tourists have found a refuge from the urban life (Daugstag 2008). Rural farms are becoming attractive tourist destinations because more visitors are nostalgic for a "quiet" life. They want to escape the hustle of city life and connect with natural and cultural heritage. In addition, tourists want to learn and meet genuine people engaged in a rural/agricultural lifestyle (Mbasera 2012). The term "rurality" is itself a specific tourist attraction. Tourists in the rural area are looking for high quality and "intact" landscape, peace, silence, as well as special kindness and contact with the host, which can be provided by agrotourism as a core product of rural tourism (Krajnović, Čičin Šain, & Predovan, 2011). Rural tourism represents a key strategy for regional development (Schubert 2006), while local population plays a very important role in the overall process. This is most commonly associated with different types of activities and services provided by farmers and rural people to attract tourists to their areas and generate extra income for their businesses (Gannon 1994).

The state has its own reasons for promoting rural tourism, such as avoiding depopulation of the countryside, protecting the natural environment and to provide income in a cheaper way for local residents, etc. (Lane 1994). Within the rural tourism, the following activities can be offered to guests: visits to farms, participation in everyday activities in the countryside, local food tasting and participation in its preparation, getting to know the village and the environment, gathering forest fruits, recreational activities (hiking, riding, biking), etc. (Bećagol 2014). The importance of history and tradition is invaluable for rural tourism, therefore the concept of rural tourism should include living history of the countryside such as rural customs and folklore, local and family traditions and the values and beliefs that make up a common heritage (Rajko 2013). Sustainability in rural tourism must be based on other principles, in addition to the principle of environmental protection. Economic sustainability implies the economic viability of the sustainable way of life and doing business. Socio-cultural aspect of sustainability implies the authenticity of family relations, compliance with customs and traditions as well as the culture of living in spiritual and material sense. The political dimension of sustainability of rural tourism refers to general support in doing business - from the local governments (villages, municipalities...), family, neighbours and so on. The support of the local governments refers to infrastructure and activities which contribute to the quality of life and working of the rural population (Kantar & Svržnjak, 2017). Taking into account all characteristics of rural tourism as Lane (1994) considers, in its purest form rural tourism should be:

- Located in rural areas.
- Functionally rural – built upon the rural world's special features of small-scale enterprise, open space, contact with nature and the natural world, heritage, —traditional societies and —traditional practices.
- Rural in scale – both in terms of buildings and settlements – and, therefore, usually small-scale.
- Traditional in character, growing slowly and organically, and connected with local families. It will often be very largely controlled locally and developed for the long-term good of the area.

2.4 Organic agriculture concept

Organic farming has originated early in the 20th century as an alternative agricultural system in reaction to rapidly changing farming practices (www.wikipedia.com). Consumers of industrialized countries have shown a great interest toward organic production in last 30 years. Food safety and quality issues have affected the awareness of people, and they start to be suspicious towards conventional products (Mutlu 2007). The term organic agriculture include the full organic and biodynamic supply chain from inputs to final manufactured goods, as well as cultural and social aspects of the movement, not just the on-farm production aspects (Kristiansen & Merfield, 2006). Organic farming is a form of farming that creates integrated, humane, environmentally and economically sustainable production systems (Lampkin 1994). Based on the principle of the International Federation of Organic Agriculture, organic agriculture is a production system that sustains the health of soils, ecosystems, and people. It relies on ecological processes, biodiversity and cycles adapted to local conditions, rather than the use of inputs with adverse effects (www.ifoam.bio).

In contrast to modern systems, organic agriculture represents a deliberate attempt to make the best use of local natural resources. The important thing for most organic farmers is that it represents a system of agriculture rather than simply a set of technologies. The primary aim is to find ways to grow food in harmony with nature (Deshmukh & Babar, 2015). According to the IFOAM organic agriculture is based on the 4 principles: principle of health, of ecology, of fairness and of care. Principle of health implies that organic agriculture should sustain and enhance the health of soil, plant, animal, human and planet as one and indivisible. Second principle emphasizes that production is to be based on ecological processes, and recycling. Those who produce, process, trade, or consume organic products should protect and benefit the common environment including landscapes, climate, habitats, biodiversity, air, and water. According to the principle of fairness, those involved in organic agriculture should conduct human relationships in a manner that ensures fairness at all levels and to all parties – farmers, workers, processors, distributors, traders, and consumers. The last principle, principle of care indicates that science is necessary to ensure that organic agriculture is healthy, safe and ecologically sound. Besides the science, this principle relates to the practical experience, accumulated wisdom and traditional and indigenous knowledge. (www.ifoam.bio). Today, there are a large number of so-called organic producers without a certificate for organic production. Consequently, there are two types of organic farming in developing countries: officially certified organic farming and informal, organic farming. The first tends to focus on the export of organic products, while the second involves small-scale activities to improve the livelihoods of individual farmers (Parror, Olesen, & Hogh-Jensen, 2006).

2.5 Relationship between rural tourism and organic agriculture

Many countries are focusing on the opportunity that the linkage of food and tourism provides and have used it as a point of competitive advantage. In research conducted in New Zeland (Steinmetz 2010) it is confirmed that the linkage of the food and tourism has the potential to increase the number of visitors to a region, extend the length of visitor stay and increase revenue generation. Organic agriculture contribution to the rural tourism development is reflected in the creation of a special niche market (Borg 2013). Organic farms can provide same tourist services and facilities as well as conventional agriculture farms, but the added value to this product gives the organic character of production. Knowing they are eating completely natural products, consumers are additionally motivated to buy healthy food (Mutlu 2007). Kristen Borg's research (May 2013) also showed that the first advantage organic farming can offer is that tourists can participate in such rural activities organized by the organizations and farmers, experience it hands-on and learn more about organic farming in Malta. The famous project in Turkey, called "Ta Tu Ta," includes farmers who receive visitors into their home in form of

"farm volunteers" or "tourists" (Tetik & Girgin, 2017). As long as tourists stay at farms, hosts can earn more income by providing accommodation and food services. Within the tourist offer, food is one of the key factors for selecting a particular destination by visitors. Many countries have recognized the importance and role of food in tourism, so they have created food strategies, which at the same time promote certain parts of that country, e.g., France, Italy and Spain use their food/wine reputation to promote tourism (du Rand & Heath, 2008). Local produce adds authenticity to the tourist experience and motivate visitors to come to a location (Sims, 2009). Food production without the use of pesticides and other chemicals contributes to the protection of the land, people, and animals on the farm. In addition to consuming organic food, through recreational activities, e.g., bike rides, horse riding, trekking, tourists breathe fresh air, and in that way contribute to improving their health (Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development 1994).

2.6 Contribution of tourism to the local community development

Tourism is a major source of employment and a central part of the economy (Ashley, Goodwin, McNab, Scott, & Chaves, 2006). It can improve local community livelihoods through employment, income generation and poverty alleviation (Privitera 2010). The potential of rural tourism to contribute to the rural community development in job creation typically occurs in the hotel and catering trades, but in the research conducted by Nara Mao (2015), about the role of tourism in poverty reduction in Siem Reap-Angkor Region in Cambodia was proved that local population have big opportunity for employment through transport. Young people can directly engage in the launch of tourism businesses, especially in small communities. Today, youth very rapidly learns foreign languages, they love to socialize and gain new experiences. Self-employment makes them independent and prevents the so-called extinguishing of the village.

Tourism encourages local residents to learn foreign languages and often provides skills training and education, so they can qualify for better-paid jobs (Honey, Vargas, & Durham, 2010). Traditional entertainments and museums are an indispensable feature of rural tourism. These events also provide the local population with the opportunity to prepare traditional food and sell organic products growing in their gardens. Tourism can revitalize traditional craft industries and provide a new market for the handicraft products (Djordjević Milošević & Milovanović, 2012). Tourism can also provide a market for agricultural products if local farmers can sell their vegetables, fruits and dairy products to hotels or restaurants that cater to tourists (Ashley et al., 2006). Farmers can also sell their product directly at the farm to tourists who are coming for a visit (Turalija, Grgić, & Zrakić, 2017). Many tourist places are known by roadside vendors (Mao 2010). Infrastructure improvements such as village paving and traffic regulation, sewage and litter disposal, can be assisted by tourism revenues and political pressure from tourism authorities. This help contributes to the value of the place itself, plays an important role in retaining existing businesses, and in attracting new enterprises and families (Government of Alberta 2010). Research in West Bengal, India has shown that the tourism development has contributed to transport facilities, communications, sanitation, living standards of local people and poverty reduction (Ray, Das, Sengupta, & Ghosh, 2012).

This research is needed to explain in which way organic agriculture can contribute to rural tourism development, and which benefits can achieve local communities by this development. This study aims to contribute to the alleviation of the unemployment problem, which is the main characteristic of the Montenegrin rural areas.

Research method

This research is conducted by the thesis that the main goal of rural development through organic production does not include the export of products abroad. The main goal implies products placement on the domestic market and organic food offer in major restaurants, hotels and rural households.

The paper set up 2 main hypotheses:

- Organic agriculture development will increase the number of tourists in rural areas.
- Rural tourism will expand organic products market.

In order to successfully achieve the main goal of this research the following methods are used:

Content analysis

The content analysis was used in order to analyze the successful practices of other countries in terms of the development of rural tourism and local communities, therefore on the basis of their experience, some similar practices are proposed for Montenegro. Based on the analysis of the content, the characteristics of the rural areas in Montenegro are presented as well as the current problems faced by organic producers.

Observation method

The researcher took part in the event organized by the "Društvo prijatelja Kolašina "(Kolašin Friends society), August 2017, in the same city. Women from Kolašin prepare food that is served on the main square, and everyone present is able to taste it. The researcher had a role of information provider about the food producers and their household location. The researcher wanted to find out if the tourists visit rural households to buy organic food?

Questionnaire

In order to determine the attitudes and preferences of the younger population, the questionnaire covered respondents of up to 35 years because this population is mostly under the influence of technology advancement, which shapes their lifestyles and creates new demands, mostly related to rural tourism. The written questionnaire was conducted in August 2017 at the territory of Montenegro. The respondents were informed that the survey is anonymous. The questionnaire consists of 10 questions, the total number of respondents is 100, out of which 49% are men while 51 % are women.

Case study

The case study method refers to the Puletić household which has been engaged in cattle breeding for almost 40 years. Four years ago they developed an attractive tourist offer, which, along with accommodation in a traditional rural environment, includes exclusively domestic food and participation in rural jobs. The household is located in the north of Montenegro, Gornje Lipovo village, Kolašin municipality, 12 kilometers away from the city. The reason for the selection of this household is to get to know their experience as the initiators of this type of business. The researcher visited Milenko and Milijanka Puletić's household in January 2018.

4. Results

Obtained results have confirmed the set up hypotheses.

Organic agriculture development will increase the number of tourist in rural areas:

Organic agriculture in rural tourism represents a new market niche. The possibility of consuming exclusively organic food satisfies special preferences of tourist therefore, their number is significantly increased. The opportunity of education on organic production directly at the farm is a new experience for tourists, which additionally motivates them to come and stay overnight. The production of typical organic products contributes to the identity and authenticity of some area, which affects increase of tourist's interest in this destination. Owners of the Puletić's household claim, the main reason that every year more and more tourists are visiting their farm is the possibility to participate in preparing organic food and doing rural jobs. Results in conducted questionnaire confirmed the same. Participation in the preparation of healthy food with the host was the most interesting activity during the visit rural households (45.4%) than followed by recreation and enjoyment at farm (30.9%).

Rural tourism will expand organic products market:

Organic products are most often sold in health food stores, but by supplying local restaurants and hotels, farmers will allow tourists to eat organic food within the hotel's offer. Many tourists have a chance to buy organic products thanks to roadside vendors. Rural households can expand organic product market like Puletić household did by providing tourists with the opportunity to eat meals prepared from organic fruits and vegetables from their own orchards and gardens. They also confirmed that a large number of tourists come to their farm exclusively to buy organic food. The event organized in Kolašin, August 2017, is one more proof that

rural tourism can expand organic product market. During the talk with the hosts, they confirmed that the same tourists who tried their cheese at the main square visited their farm just to buy it.

The results of the research also showed that the future development of villages and agriculture in the northern region of Montenegro largely inhibits the insufficient number of working-age population. This lack is caused by a high migration rate in the search for a job. A large number of households consists of only 1 or 2 members, mostly aged 60 and over, who are not able to deal with agriculture not even for their household needs. Empty households close the door to the development of tourism and the trend of extinguishing Montenegrin villages continues.

5. Discussion

5.1 The necessity of reviving villages

In this case, revival involves stopping migrations from villages to cities and launching agricultural production. Revival would contribute to resolving the unemployment problem the population of Montenegro is facing a longer period of time. However, the main problem is that young people are not at all interested in rural life and dealing with agricultural activities. Even those who were born and grew up in the countryside have completely excluded this option as a possibility of employment.

The results of this research have shown that organic agriculture has a great potential to create new tourist product and provide new workplace. The fact that 98% of tourists would again visit the same rural household is talking about the role of these households in the development of rural tourism itself. Among the rare who recognized value of family holding itself are Milijanka and Milenko Puletić who said that they are very grateful to tourists, without their help they wouldn't realize how much each inch of their farm is worth. The experience of the Puletić's household has confirmed that small rural households have enormous potential to develop private business through organic agriculture. Every member of the Puletić family works on their own holding, and there is no financial crisis for them, confirmed the hosts. However, organic production in Montenegro is still at the beginning. According to monteorganica (company for controlling and issuing certificates in organic agriculture in Montenegro), there are 354 organic producers registered, more than 120 are in Bijelo Polje (www.orgcg.org).

5.2 Obstacles on the development of organic agriculture in Montenegro

Data obtained found out that the obstacles on the development of organic agriculture in Montenegro are numerous. It has not begun to live as a possibility for the development of a private business yet. Moreover, the youth are ashamed of dealing with agriculture, because they lack the information and experience about its significance and the benefits it provides. It has led to a high migration rate and a deficit of young workforce in rural areas of Montenegro. Results of this research also show that the holding fragmentation is one more important problem of the organic agriculture development. It affects producers to produce only for household needs. The organic products market in Montenegro almost does not exist. Government support for smaller organic food producers is insufficient. Rural households are not promoted in an appropriate way, while domestic organic products are not protected- imported products are significantly cheaper. Insufficient education on organic agriculture of the labor force on family farms is another one cause of the organic agriculture stagnation.

5.3 The significance of participation in organic farming activities

In order to significantly influence the awareness of the youth about the importance of organic agriculture, first, it should start from the pupils in elementary school, like it has done in Denver, USA by turning an unused grassy field into an organic garden (www.zdravahrana.com). The children would have the opportunity to participate in the cultivation of the land, see how the vegetables grow and participate in its cultivation. In this way, the school saves its money, by supplying the school dining with organic products at a minimum price, since it produces

them. This project is a great experience both in the emotional and educational sense because it greatly stimulates the interest of city children not only to make organic vegetables but also to eat them!

It is important to allow the children to experience organic agriculture, to feel its beauty instead of experiencing it as shame and hard work. It would be the best to provide them with the opportunity to visit organic farms. Carolin Wacher in the research on the development of agro-tourism on organic farms in the new EU-Poland, Estonia, and Slovenia (2006) countries shared similar example (Wacher 2006). Thus children can try new food, have contact with animals and learn a lot of useful things about organic agriculture during the talk with the farmers. This practice would be a great opportunity for children in Montenegro to fall in love with organic agriculture and stay on family holdings.

Similarly to the Ta Tu Ta project in Turkey (Tetik & Girgin, 2010), it should provide the opportunity for the potential farmers to stay and participate in all agricultural activities on large organic farms. In addition to participating in the entire process of organic production, they would have the opportunity to communicate with tourists. In this way, they would be convinced that the combination of rural tourism and organic agriculture brings high incomes. It would motivate them not to leave their holdings, but to develop private businesses. This is a great way to overcome the embarrassment of rural life and dealing with farming.

5.4 Merging small real estates as a solution for land fragmentation

Fragmentation of soil in Montenegro prevents producers to produce in large quantities. Local population should be introduced to the “merge” of several real estates into big one like it is done in Kerun Morden Agricultural Park, located in China, the province of Hubei, Jingzhou. This practice works in the following way: main owner rents real estates from several farmers and employs a large number of local people at that same big holding. The owner pays a lease to farmers on an annual basis, and the opportunity of working on the holding provides them with additional income. The same method should be applied in Montenegro. Owners of small real estate mainly produce only for household needs, but now they would be able to earn money on an annual basis, as well as the salary every month for working on the holding.

5.5 Expansion of the organic products market as a prerequisite for the development of organic agriculture

Research on the consumers habits in Montenegro has shown that (42%) of those who do not buy domestic products comment that these products are not always available. As soon as organic products are not available, and awareness about their importance low, consumers, will not try to find them by themselves. Therefore, it is necessary to expand the market of organic products in order to be consumed primarily by the inhabitants of Montenegro. If domestic tourists do not buy them, it cannot be expected from foreigners. Foremost, it is necessary to create a marketplace for organic products in Montenegro. When the consciousness of domestic tourists about the importance of organic food is increased, then the owners of large restaurants and hotels will be forced to buy domestic healthy products. In that way, the organic market is expanding, and the producers are motivated to produce more. In Italy, organic products are mostly sold in National Parks (Grandi & Triantafyllidis, 2010). The five National parks in Montenegro should be used to expand the market for organic products. It is necessary to support the creation of farmers' markets within the park, promote the use of park products in local schools and sell through park structures such as the restaurants, "Visitors Center," information offices... As a result of this practice, the number of tourists in protected areas would be considerably increased.

5.6 Internet, national television and public interactive workshops as the most powerful means to promoting organic products and rural households

Insufficient support by the Government to organic producers (low subsidies, inadequate promotion, and protection of Montenegrin organic products) has affected its low demand and distrust in quality among the consumers. Those who do not buy domestic products, also believe that imported products are cheaper (20%), (18%) think that imported products are of better quality, while (11.3%) have a habit of buy imported products. It is unacceptable that in an ecological state that has perfect natural and climatic conditions for the development of organic agriculture, imported products have an advantage. First of all, the Government should better promote

organic products, e.g., on national television to make a commercial (Let's support domestic, live healthy) and alike. It would affect changes in consumer habits. Also, in order to reduce consumer's distrust in the quality of domestic products, there should be organized the public interactive workshops with the aim of educating the general public about recognizing organic products and distinguishing from conventional and false organic, manner of production, control and certification as well as about the protection of the right of consumers of organic food. A similar event was organized in Serbia in 2017 (www.agropress.org.rs).

There are some rural households in Montenegro that offer organic food and accommodation services, but the main reason why tourists do not know about these households is their poor promotion. Today, the internet is the most powerful tool for direct promotion. Based on the successful experience of France (Radonjić 2011), the National Tourism Organization of Montenegro should establish a central reservation system throughout Montenegro, which enables the direct booking of any rural household that is a member of the same association.

5.7 Adaptation of the salaš in order to satisfy the special tourist's preferences

The results of the conducted questionnaire revealed that during the stay in the rural areas (54, 2%) of respondents would stay overnight in the hut while (30, 2%) opted for the host home. Only (10, 2%) would like to stay in local hotel. It indicates that tourists are more interested in the traditional type of accommodation. There are a lot of "salaš" in Montenegro which most often serve as storage space, while the old hosts lead a difficult battle to build new accommodation capacities or renovate older houses. The use of salaš can be a great opportunity for the rural households to satisfy specific preferences of the tourist. In order to improve the future development of the rural households in addition to the roads improvement (38, 8%), tourist suggested preservation of traditional house appearance (20, 4%), the same percent propose better promotion of rural households. "It is only necessary to clean the salaš and free the spirit of life from the distant past." In the salaš, the food is prepared from organic fruits and vegetables from surrounding gardens. Visitors have the opportunity to cultivate the land, and they also can learn traditional crafts as well as traditional songs and customs, during the organized entertainments. In Hungary, life in salaš was an unforgettable experience for many visitors (Banić, Grubišić, & Antonijević, 2013). The salaš activation in the tourist offer would provide tourists to experience the way of life of Montenegrin ancestors, which implied the common life of the whole family in the salaš, as well as the cultivation of the surrounding land.

One of the long-standing problems of the underdevelopment of the northern region of Montenegro is in the process of resolving. It is about big project, the construction of a highway, which will enable the infrastructure connection of the north and south of Montenegro. Tourists will have an unseen opportunity, that in less than 90 minutes from the mountains they reach the impeccable beaches. Farmers will also be able to supply coastal cities with healthy food on a daily basis. In this way, the organic food market will expand to the southern region also. Montenegro is not a member of the EU yet, and its accession will greatly contribute to both organic agriculture and tourism.

6. Conclusion

Combined with organic agriculture, tourism has great potential to increase revenue of the local population, employment rate and number of young workforce in rural areas, as well as to reduce migration to cities and import of agricultural products. This study has confirmed that currently, organic agriculture has the greatest role in increasing the number of tourist in rural areas. Data also shows that the market for organic products is significantly expanding within rural tourism.

In order to bridge the gap between the northern and southern region, it is needed to enrich the offer and develop product to motivate tourists to enjoy Montenegro even out of the main season. Visitors should be given a chance to discover beauties of the Montenegrin villages, their tradition, and culture. Regarding the development of organic agriculture, financial, educational and professional assistance should be provided to rural households. As to make youth closer with organic agriculture and encourage them to develop a private business it is needed to provide them with the possibility to visit organic farms and attend public events on organic agriculture. National

television and internet are the most powerful promotional channels which should be used to change consumer habits and promote rural households. Organic agriculture can be remedy for reviving neglected rural areas in Montenegro and great opportunity for rural households to develop private business.

This article opens door for future research. However, it is necessary to mention certain limitations during the conduct of the research. In the preliminary studies linkage of organic production and development of rural tourism is poorly explained, so it is difficult to assess the other countries experience within this regard. The researcher stayed in Montenegro for a short period of time, so, it was not possible to apply the method of a case study involving more households, and compare their attitudes and experiences. The research highlights the benefits of rural tourism and organic production, but the negative effects that arise in their development are missing.

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